

Original article

Age-related divergent remodeling of the cardiac extracellular matrix in heart failure: Collagen accumulation in the young and loss in the aged

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ABSTRACT

The incidence of heart failure (HF) increases with age. This study sought to determine whether aging exacerbates structural and functional remodeling of the myocardium in HF. HF was induced in young (~18 months) and aged sheep (>8 years) by right ventricular tachypacing. In non-paced animals, aging was associated with increased left ventricular (LV) end diastolic internal dimensions (EDID, $P < 0.001$), reduced fractional shortening ($P < 0.01$) and an increase in myocardial collagen content ($P < 0.01$). HF increased EDID and reduced fractional shortening in both young and aged animals, although these changes were more pronounced in the aged ($P < 0.05$). Age-associated differences in cardiac extracellular matrix (ECM) remodeling occurred in HF with collagen accumulation in young HF ($P < 0.001$) and depletion in aged HF ($P < 0.05$). MMP-2 activity increased in the aged control and young HF groups ($P < 0.05$). Reduced tissue inhibitor of metalloproteinase (TIMP) expression (TIMPs 3 and 4, $P < 0.05$) was present only in the aged HF group. Secreted protein acidic and rich in cysteine (SPARC) was increased in aged hearts compared to young controls ($P < 0.05$) while serum procollagen type I C-pro peptide (PICP) was increased in both young failing ($P < 0.05$) and aged failing ($P < 0.01$) animals. In conclusion, collagen content of the cardiac ECM changes in both aging and HF although; whether collagen accumulation or depletion occurs depends on age. Changes in TIMP expression in aged failing hearts alongside augmented collagen synthesis in HF provide a potential mechanism for the age-dependent ECM remodeling. Aging should therefore be considered an important factor when elucidating cardiac disease mechanisms.

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1. Introduction

Heart failure (HF) is predominantly a disease of the elderly [1] which results in structural and functional remodeling of the myocardium. Alterations to the properties of the cardiac extracellular matrix (ECM), which consists of predominantly fibrillar collagen [2], are central to this remodeling process *e.g.* [3,4]. The cardiac ECM serves to maintain correct myocyte geometry and cardiac extension properties, and provides tensile strength to the tissue. As such it can directly alter both the systolic and diastolic function of the heart [5] even in the absence of myocyte contractile dysfunction [6] with the collagen type III:I ratio inversely correlating with ventricular function [7]. As a general rule collagen accumulation, or interstitial fibrosis, results in ventricular stiffening and reduced compliance of the myocardium [8], whereas collagen loss promotes myocyte slippage and ventricular dilatation [3,9].

Maintenance of ECM homeostasis is achieved through a balance between collagen synthesis and degradation. The matrix metalloproteinases

(MMPs) are the key enzymes responsible for ECM degradation whereas the tissue inhibitors of metalloproteinases (TIMPs) endogenously inhibit this process. Although it is known that remodeling of the myocardial ECM occurs in HF, a consensus on the nature of these alterations does not exist, with some evidence favoring fibrosis at the point of end-stage HF [10–12], and others depicting collagen depletion [13–15]. This is likely reflective of the animal model used, underlying pathological process as well as changes to the balance between collagen synthesis and degradation [3,4,11,13].

It has been commonly observed that in aging, fibrosis leads to increased passive stiffness of the myocardium and impaired diastolic function *e.g.* [16,17] and the MMP and TIMP profile prior to the onset of cardiac disease can dramatically alter the response of the ECM to injury [18–21]. Therefore, the changes to the myocardial MMP–TIMP profile and the consequent effects on myocardial collagen content that occur in aging [22], are likely to have a profound influence on the outcome of ECM remodeling occurring in response to cardiac insult. However, as the majority of studies have been carried out using young animal models of HF, the mechanism of disease progression on an aging substrate has not yet been addressed. Crucially, the role of the ECM in the pathogenesis of

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HF in the aged myocardium remains to be determined. In the present study, we have employed a large animal model of ventricular tachypacing, in order to investigate whether and to what extent aging alters the response of the cardiac ECM in the development of HF. The findings from this study suggest that the response of the myocardial ECM to rapid pacing-induced HF is highly dependent on age.

2. Methods

An expanded methods section is provided in the online supplementary material.

All procedures involving the use of animals were performed in accordance with The United Kingdom Animals (Scientific Procedures) Act, 1986 and conform to the Guide for the Care and Use of Laboratory Animals published by the US National Institutes of Health (NIH Publication No. 85-23, revised 1996).

2.1. Experimental model of aging and heart failure

HF was induced in 25 female Welsh Mountain sheep (37.4 ± 1.2 kg) aged either 18–24 months (young) or >8 years (aged, last quintile of normal life expectancy [23]) by 31.8 ± 0.9 days of right ventricular tachypacing at $210 \text{ beats min}^{-1}$ using a method described previously [24,25]. Following tachypacing, final *in vivo* measurements were made and then animals were killed (heparin 10,000 units and pentobarbitone sodium 200 mg kg^{-1} intravenously).

2.2. Echocardiography and blood pressure

Cardiac geometry and contractility were assessed by trans-thoracic echocardiography performed on conscious, supine animals as described previously [24,25]. Indirect blood pressure (BP) measurements were made from the coccygeal artery using tail cuff plethysmography in standing animals (Cardell, Sharn USA).

2.3. Histological assessment of collagen content

For histological analysis of collagen content, full-thickness sections of the left ventricular (LV) free wall were stained with picosirius red (PSR) and interstitial collagen visualized using polarized light microscopy as described previously [3]. Collagen content is expressed as percentage collagen-containing pixels per tissue section area [3].

2.4. Gelatin zymography

LV tissue was snap frozen in liquid nitrogen and gelatin zymography performed as described previously [3]. Protein samples ($20 \mu\text{g}$) were separated using non-reducing SDS-PAGE containing 1 mg ml^{-1} gelatin. Each sample was repeated in triplicate and zymographic band intensity normalized to an internal standard common to each gel (prepared from LV tissue from a non-experimental young control animal). Confirmation that lytic bands were produced by MMPs was performed by incubating a parallel zymogram in incubation buffer containing EDTA (10 mmol l^{-1}). The EDTA chelates the calcium necessary for MMP activity and thus inhibits gelatinase-dependent gelatin degradation. Differentiation between pro- and active MMPs was carried out using a p-aminophenylmercuric acetate (APMA, 10 mmol l^{-1}) activation assay as previously described [3]. Briefly, the APMA will activate any MMPs present in their pro-form using HT-1080 conditioned media (a source of MMPs 2 and 9 [26]) as a positive control. If the MMP present is already in its active form, no shift in band weight will occur upon incubation with APMA compared to without APMA.

2.5. Immunoblotting

TIMP-1, 2, 3, and 4 as well as secreted protein acidic and rich in cysteine (SPARC) protein levels were measured by immunoblotting. LV protein extracts were prepared as described previously [3,27,28]. Samples were separated by reducing SDS-PAGE before transferring to nitrocellulose membranes. Details of immunoblotting conditions are described in Supplementary Material Table 1. Each sample was repeated in triplicate and protein levels normalized to an internal standard common to each blot (LV tissue from a non-experimental young control animal). In preliminary studies we found that the expression levels of the so-called ‘housekeeping’ proteins β -actin and glyceraldehyde 3-phosphate dehydrogenase (GAPDH) are altered in aging and HF [24] (data not shown). However, following transfer to nitrocellulose, all blots are stained with Ponceau-S to ensure even gel loading and transfer (data not shown).

2.6. qPCR

cDNA was prepared from $1 \mu\text{g}$ total RNA isolated from sheep LV using Invitrogen Superscript III (Life Technologies, California). Ovis aries type I collagen- α precursor (Col1A1) mRNA expression was measured using an Applied Biosystems StepOnePlus™ real-time machine (Life Technologies, California) and primer sequences obtained from Jarvis et al. [29]. mRNA expression was measured using Applied Biosystems Power SYBR Green PCR Mastermix fluorescent incorporation (Life Technologies, California) and normalized to ribosomal 28S housekeeping gene.

2.7. Biochemical measurement of collagen fibril formation

Venous blood samples were collected from the jugular vein in experimental animals both pre-pacing and at the point of HF. Samples were spun at $4000 \times g$ for 10 min to obtain serum. Serum was snap-frozen and stored in liquid nitrogen. Procollagen type I carboxy-terminal pro peptide (PICP) was measured from sheep serum using a specific ELISA according to the manufacturer's instructions (Takara Bio Inc, Japan). Serum PICP concentration was quantified from duplicate samples versus a standard curve constructed using PICP standards. The minimum detection level for the assay was 10 ng/ml .

2.8. Data analysis

Data obtained from *in vivo* measurements, as well as quantification of serum PICP levels, were from the same animal and are therefore paired data sets *i.e.* before tachypacing and at the point of HF. Assessments of collagen content, MMPs, TIMPs, SPARC and collagen type I mRNA required the used of post mortem myocardial tissue samples, and were therefore obtained from separate sets of control young and control aged animals. All data is represented as mean \pm standard error of the mean (SEM) of n animals. Unpaired data was assessed using a 2-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) whereas paired data were analyzed using a 2-way repeated measures ANOVA. Data that was not normally distributed was transformed by means appropriate to the spread of data (square or reciprocal) prior to statistical analyses. Correlations between linear regressions were performed using Pearson's coefficient. Differences were considered significant at $P < 0.05$.

3. Results

Following tachypacing, both young and aged animals displayed clinical symptoms of biventricular failure including dyspnea and ascites and pulmonary edema.

Fig. 1. Impaired contractility and ventricular dilatation in aging and heart failure. Representative m-mode echocardiograms taken proximal to the papillary muscle from young pre-paced, young failing, old pre-paced, and old failing animals. Open arrow, septum endocardial surface; and solid arrow, left ventricular free wall endocardial surface.

3.1. Aging accentuates gross structural remodeling and contractile dysfunction in heart failure

Trans-thoracic echocardiography was performed on 15 young and 10 aged animals prior to implantation of cardiac pacemakers (pre-pacing) and following tachypacing-induced HF (post-pacing). Due to the anatomical arrangement of the cardiac apex over the sternum in the sheep, trans-thoracic four-chamber apical views were unobtainable, thus precluding measurement of cardiac mass, volumes and ejection fraction. Instead, measurements were made from right-sided parasternal long-axis and short-axis views. Representative m-mode echocardiograms are illustrated in Fig. 1 and the data is summarized in Table 1.

Of particular note, LV end diastolic internal dimension (EDID) was increased by $32 \pm 9.9\%$ in aging ($P < 0.001$) while fractional shortening assessed from long-axis m-mode echocardiograms was reduced by $14 \pm 3.8\%$ ($P < 0.01$). Similarly, the fractional area change obtained from short-axis coronal views at the level of the papillary muscle tip also showed a $14 \pm 2.8\%$ reduction in aging ($P < 0.05$). In addition to changes in LV function and geometry, aging also resulted in a 7.6 ± 3.4 mmHg increase in diastolic BP and 7.2 ± 3.3 mmHg rise in mean arterial pressure (both $P < 0.05$).

Tachypacing in young animals resulted in a $61 \pm 10.6\%$ increase in EDID and a $55 \pm 2.4\%$ decrease in fractional shortening (both $P < 0.001$) and aged tachypaced animals displayed a $29 \pm 10.1\%$ increase in EDID and a $62 \pm 4.7\%$ decrease in fractional shortening (both $P < 0.001$). LV chamber diameter and contractile dysfunction were greatest in aged animals following tachypacing (both $P < 0.05$). Fractional area change was reduced with tachypacing in young and aged animals by $46 \pm 5.2\%$ and $46 \pm 5.2\%$, respectively (both $P < 0.001$). In addition, tachypacing led to

similar decreases in systolic, diastolic and mean BP in both young and aged animals (all $P < 0.001$).

3.2. Alterations to LV collagen content in heart failure are age-dependent

The interstitial LV collagen matrix was assessed using histological methods, which, unlike biochemical techniques, enables the exclusion of non-interstitial collagen (epicardial, endocardial and perivascular). Tissue sections visualized by light microscopy revealed an extensive collagen network in the ovine LV and demonstrated that interstitial fibrosis was evident in both aging and after tachypacing in young animals (Fig. 2A, arrows). Conversely, the collagen network was markedly depleted in aged tachypaced animals (Fig. 2Aiv/viii).

Mean interstitial collagen content was quantified as the non-vascular myocardial collagen and therefore also excluded endocardial and epicardial regions, and expressed as percentage collagen-containing pixels per tissue section area (Fig. 2B) [3]. Aging resulted in increased collagen content compared to young controls ($2.3 \pm 0.4\%$ vs. $1.0 \pm 0.14\%$, $n = 5$, $P < 0.01$). Conversely, a divergent response of the matrix occurred following tachypacing, with collagen accumulation in the young HF group ($2.6 \pm 0.28\%$ vs. $1.0 \pm 0.14\%$, $n = 5-8$, $P < 0.001$) and collagen loss in the aged HF group ($1.2 \pm 0.25\%$ vs. $2.3 \pm 0.4\%$, $n = 5-6$, $P < 0.05$). Importantly, the collagen content in the aged HF myocardium was also less than that in the young HF animals ($P < 0.01$).

The relationship between myocardial collagen content, LV diastolic dimensions and fractional shortening is shown in Figs. 2C and D. Again, there is an age-dependent divergent response to tachypacing. With the induction of HF, chamber dilatation and reduced fractional shortening occur in parallel to increased collagen content in the young (Fig. 2C) and decreased collagen content in the aged (Fig. 2D).

Table 1
Echocardiographic and hemodynamic measurements.

	Young (n = 15)			Aged (n = 10)		
	Pre-paced	Post-paced	Δ (%)	Pre-paced	Post-paced	Δ (%)
EDID (cm)	2.5 ± 0.12	$3.8 \pm 0.07^{***}$	61.1 ± 10.6	$3.3 \pm 0.19^{***}$	$4.2 \pm 0.13^{\dagger\dagger\dagger, \#}$	29.2 ± 10.1
ESID (cm)	0.8 ± 0.07	$2.7 \pm 0.09^{***}$	248.1 ± 26.9	$1.4 \pm 0.15^{**}$	$3.3 \pm 0.19^{\dagger\dagger\dagger, \#\#}$	156.1 ± 28.1
Fractional shortening	0.7 ± 0.02	$0.3 \pm 0.02^{***}$	-55.2 ± 2.4	$0.6 \pm 0.02^{**}$	$0.2 \pm 0.02^{\dagger\dagger\dagger, \#}$	-62.0 ± 4.7
RWT	1.0 ± 0.10	$0.4 \pm 0.03^{***}$	-49.7 ± 6.3	0.7 ± 0.08	$0.5 \pm 0.07^{\dagger\dagger}$	-34.4 ± 5.6
Fractional area change	0.7 ± 0.02	$0.4 \pm 0.02^{***}$	-42.1 ± 4.3	$0.6 \pm 0.01^*$	$0.3 \pm 0.03^{\dagger\dagger}$	-45.5 ± 5.2
Systolic BP (mmHg)	125.8 ± 2.6	$111.0 \pm 2.7^{***}$	-11.7 ± 1.8	132.2 ± 2.6	$116.9 \pm 2.9^{\dagger\dagger}$	-11.4 ± 2.2
Diastolic BP (mmHg)	78.5 ± 1.9	$69.0 \pm 1.4^{***}$	-11.6 ± 2.9	$86.1 \pm 2.8^*$	$71.3 \pm 3.2^{\dagger\dagger\dagger}$	-17.1 ± 2.6
Mean BP (mmHg)	94.3 ± 2.0	$83.0 \pm 1.7^{***}$	-11.7 ± 2.3	$101.5 \pm 2.6^*$	$86.5 \pm 2.7^{\dagger\dagger\dagger}$	-14.7 ± 1.8

Values are mean \pm SEM. * $P < 0.05$ vs. young pre-paced. ** $P < 0.01$ vs. young pre-paced. *** $P < 0.001$ vs. young pre-paced. $\dagger P < 0.01$ vs. old pre-paced. $\dagger\dagger P < 0.001$ vs. old pre-paced. $\# P < 0.05$ vs. young post-paced. $\#\# P < 0.01$ vs. young post-paced. EDID, end diastolic internal diameter. ESID, end systolic internal diameter. Fractional shortening calculated as (EDID subtract ESID) divided by EDID. RWT (relative wall thickness) calculated as ($2 \times$ diastolic wall thickness) divided by EDID. Fractional area change calculated as (end diastolic area subtract end systolic area) divided by end diastolic area. BP, blood pressure.

Fig. 2. Age-associated differences in remodeling of the collagen matrix in heart failure. (A) Representative picosirius red (PSR) stained micrographs imaged at $\times 20$ magnification in bright field (Ai–iv) and circularly polarized light (Av–viii) from young control (YC: Ai, Av), young failing (YF: Aii, Avii), old control (OC: Aiii, Aviii) and old failing (OF: Aiv, viii) animals. Pixels positive for collagen appear red/yellow/green in the polarized images (arrows). (B) Collagen content determined from histological sections expressed as mean \pm SEM of $n =$ YC = 5, YF = 8, OC = 5 and OF = 6. The relationship between collagen content and ventricular shape and function is depicted for (C) young, and (D) aged animals. Data points are mean \pm SEM for n of YC = 5 (collagen) and 15 (echo), YF = 8 (collagen) and 15 (echo), OC = 5 (collagen) and 10 (echo) and OF = 6 (collagen) and 10 (echo). ** $P < 0.01$ vs. YC. *** $P < 0.001$ vs. YC. † $P < 0.05$ vs. OC. ## $P < 0.01$ vs. YF. Data symbols: open circle, YC; solid circle, YF; open triangle, OC; and solid triangle, OF. EDID, end diastolic internal dimension.

3.3. Changes to MMP activity alone cannot explain the age-dependent response of the collagen matrix in heart failure

Since aging leads to a differential response of the collagen matrix to tachypacing-induced HF, the next series of experiments were carried out to investigate whether the regulation of ECM turnover in HF is influenced by age. MMP activity in ventricular tissue was assessed using gelatin zymography. Fig. 3Ai shows a representative zymogram illustrating gelatinolytic activity at ~ 68 kDa corresponding

to MMP-2 (commercial standard not shown). No additional gelatinolytic activity was seen at other molecular weights suggesting that MMP-2 is the major gelatinase involved in the LV remodeling response in the sheep. This was confirmed by running LV extracts alongside ovine lung tissue as a positive control which shows the presence of MMP-9 (see Supplementary Fig. 3). Gelatinolytic activity due to MMP-2 was abolished by pre-incubation with EDTA (10 mmol l^{-1} , Fig. 3Aii). Fig. 3B demonstrates that the gelatinolytic activity of MMP-2 was due to the active rather than the pro-form of

Fig. 3. MMP-2 activity is elevated in aging and heart failure. (A) Representative gelatin zymograms (i) from YC, YF, OC and OF LV protein extracts. (ii) Gelatinolytic activity was confirmed by incubating a parallel gel with EDTA. (B) Zymogram of HT-1080 conditioned media (gray bar) and LV extracts from YC (open bar), YF (striped bar) and OC (solid bar) pre-incubated in the presence (+) or absence (-) of *p*-aminophenylmercuric acetate (APMA). (C) MMP-2 activity quantified by densitometry and expressed as mean pixel density (relative to an internal standard – LV tissue from a young control sheep not used in the current study) \pm SEM of $n = \text{YC} = 7$, $\text{YF} = 7$, $\text{OC} = 8$ and $\text{OF} = 6$. * $P < 0.05$ vs. YC. ** $P < 0.01$ vs. YC.

the enzyme since incubation with APMA (10 mmol l^{-1}) failed to induce a shift in band weights in ovine LV extracts, despite activation of pro-MMP-2 in the HT-1080 conditioned media. Gelatinase activity was also the same molecular weight as MMP-2 in the HT-1080 conditioned media positive control.

Summary data for MMP-2 activity is presented in Fig. 3C and expressed as a ratio to an internal standard. Compared to the young control animals, MMP-2 activity was increased in both the young HF (1.7 ± 0.14 vs. 1.0 ± 0.22 , $n = 7$, $P < 0.01$) and aged control myocardium (1.5 ± 0.08 vs. 1.0 ± 0.22 , $n = 7-8$, $P < 0.05$). However, there was no further augmentation of MMP-2 activity in the aged HF samples.

3.4. Reduced TIMP expression is present only in aged failing hearts

The age- and disease-dependent alterations to total MMP activity are therefore inconsistent with the changes to myocardial collagen content occurring in aging and HF. The next series of experiments sought to determine if the levels of TIMPs (which regulate MMP activity) were altered by aging and/or disease and if this provides a mechanism for the preferential accumulation of collagen in the young HF animals and loss of collagen in the aged HF animals. Fig. 4A shows representative immunoblots for TIMP-1, 2, 3 and 4 levels. By two-way ANOVA, no differences in TIMP-1 (Fig. 4B) or TIMP-2 (Fig. 4C) were evident in either aging or HF. However, both TIMP-3 (Fig. 4D; aged HF, 1.1 ± 0.04 ; aged control 1.5 ± 0.12 ; young HF, 1.5 ± 0.16 ; young control, 1.7 ± 0.3 , $n = 5-10$) and TIMP-4 (Fig. 4E; aged HF, 1.1 ± 0.06 , aged control, 1.8 ± 0.15 ; young HF, 2.3 ± 0.26 ; young control 1.9 ± 0.2 , $n = 5-8$) levels were reduced only in the aged failing myocardium ($P < 0.05$).

Fig. 4. TIMPs 3 and 4 are reduced only in aged animals with heart failure. (A) Representative Western blots for TIMP-1, TIMP-2, TIMP-3 and TIMP-4 from YC, YF, OC and OF LV extracts. Protein levels were quantified by densitometry for TIMP-1 (B), TIMP-2 (C), TIMP-3 (D) and TIMP-4 (E). Data is expressed as mean \pm SEM of $n = \text{YC} = 5$, $\text{YF} = 8$, $\text{OC} = 5$ and $\text{OF} = 6$ ($n = 10$ for TIMP-3). † $P < 0.05$ vs. OC. # $P < 0.05$ vs. YF. ## $P < 0.01$ vs. YF.

Fig. 5. Relationship between TIMP protein levels and MMP-2 activity. (A) Correlation between MMP-2 activity and TIMP-3 protein was not significant. (B) Elevated MMP-2 activity was significantly correlated with a decrease in TIMP-4 protein. Closed symbols represent paired data points from n of YC=3 (4 for TIMP-4), YF=2, OC=3 and OF=6; open symbols represent mean values from each experimental group where n of YC=7 (MMP) and 5 (TIMP), YF=7 (MMP) and 8 (TIMP), OC=8 (MMP) and 5 (TIMP) and OF=6 (MMP) and 10 (TIMP-3; 6 for TIMP-4). Circle = YC, square = YF, upwards triangle = OC and downwards triangle = OF. Regression lines have been fit to all data points.

We next sought to determine whether the reduction in TIMP-3 and TIMP-4 protein inversely correlates with the augmented MMP-2 activity measured by zymography. These relationships are depicted in Fig. 5. Despite the reduction of TIMP-3 in the aged HF myocardium, this was not correlated with increased MMP-2 activity (Fig. 5A: slope = -0.234 ± 0.15 , $n = 14$, $P = 0.138$). Conversely, a significant correlation was detected between TIMP-4 levels and MMP-2 activity (Fig. 5B: slope = -0.325 ± 0.14 , $n = 15$, $P < 0.05$) in ovine myocardium.

3.5. Collagen processing and fibrillogenesis is altered in aging and heart failure

While diminished TIMP expression provides one mechanism by which a reduction in collagen content may occur in the aged, failing hearts, changes to collagen degradation pathways alone cannot explain why myocardial fibrosis is present in young paced, and aged control animals. The next set of experiments sought to determine if alterations to collagen synthesis and/or processing may explain these changes. Although qPCR data (Fig. 6A) did not reach significance, there is a trend towards an increase in collagen type I mRNA expression in HF versus control in both young and aged sheep ($P = 0.079$).

Fig. 6Bi depicts a representative immunoblot for SPARC, a collagen-binding matricellular protein involved in post-synthetic collagen processing and thus formation of mature collagen fibrils [30,31]. SPARC expression was increased in aged animals compared to young (Fig. 6Bii: 1.6 ± 0.37 vs. 0.9 ± 0.17 , $n = 6$, $P < 0.05$), however no change in SPARC was detected with disease. Furthermore, SPARC levels in aged failing animals were not altered compared to aged control, or young HF ($P = 0.735$ and $P = 0.191$, respectively).

Finally, collagen fibrillogenesis was quantified indirectly by measuring the presence of PICP in sheep serum samples (Fig. 6C). Serum PICP was increased in young HF compared to young controls (1067 ± 247 ng/ml vs. 465 ± 84 ng/ml, $n = 6$, $P < 0.05$) and also in

Fig. 6. Collagen deposition and processing is altered in aging and heart failure. (Ai) Agarose gel illustrating a single product from Col1A1 primers and ovine cDNA (–, without reverse transcriptase; ±, with reverse transcriptase). (ii) Collagen type I mRNA measured using qPCR was not significantly altered in aging and/or heart failure. $n = YC = 5$, $YF = 5$, $OC = 5$ and $OF = 6$. (B) Representative immunoblot for SPARC extracted from LV tissue samples is depicted in (i). (ii) Bands were quantified by densitometry relative to an internal standard. $n = 6$ per group. (C) Procollagen type I C-peptide was quantified from sheep serum using a specific ELISA assay. $n = 6$ per group. * $P < 0.05$ vs. YC. †† $P < 0.01$ vs. OC.

aged HF versus aged controls (1340 ± 204 ng/ml vs. 574 ± 137 ng/ml, $n = 6$, $P < 0.01$). PICP concentration however was not higher in aged HF versus young HF animals ($P = 0.297$).

4. Discussion

Remodeling of the cardiac ECM is believed to directly contribute to the deterioration of myocardial function which occurs in HF. However, whether aging *per se* influences the response of the cardiac ECM to HF is largely unknown. The present study investigates the impact of aging and HF on the collagen content of the cardiac ECM and has five major findings: i) aging results in cardiac enlargement and reduced contractility, ii) tachypacing-induced HF leads to collagen accumulation in young animals and collagen depletion in aged animals, iii) compared to young control samples, MMP-2 activity is increased in the young HF, aged control and aged HF myocardium, iv) TIMPs 3 and 4 are decreased only in the aged failing myocardium, and v) collagen processing and fibrillogenesis is altered as result of aging and disease. We propose that, for a given cardiac insult leading to the development of HF, the altered profile of MMP activity, TIMP expression and collagen processing which occurs in aging, predispose the aged heart to greater functional remodeling and changes in collagen content in the opposite direction to those seen in young hearts.

4.1. Cardiac remodeling in aging and heart failure

Cardiac dilatation and reduced contractile function are hallmarks of tachycardic and dilated cardiomyopathy [32]. Due to the ovine anatomical arrangement whereby the cardiac apex lies directly underneath the sternum, we were unable to measure ventricular volumes and thus ejection fraction. However by using parasternal long-axis images, we have established that the above hallmarks are present in the current ovine model of tachypacing-induced HF. Similar, albeit far less pronounced, structural and functional remodeling also occurs in the aged heart e.g. Lindsey et al. [22] and Sangaralingham et al. [33]. However, whether the changes in LV structure and function that occur in aging influence the response of the myocardium to a disease-causing insult remain very poorly understood. In a single study of canine experimental ischemia and reperfusion, where hearts were studied 3 days after reperfusion, aged animals demonstrated greater infarct size and chamber dilatation than young animals [34]. While this suggests the importance ECM degradative pathways in an aged model of ischemia-reperfusion injury, no long-term follow up data on cardiac remodeling or HF progression was available for this study. Conversely, in a model of myocardial ischemia in the rat, no age-dependent changes in cardiac remodeling were noted [35]. However, in this latter study the original cardiac insult was produced in 'middle-aged' (18 month old) rather than aged rats. As such the extent of myocardial remodeling present at the time of 'injury' may be less than that in either the present study or that of Jugdutt et al. [34], with consequent effects for the extent of remodeling occurring after the injury.

4.2. Age-dependent ECM remodeling in heart failure

A striking observation in the present study is the diametrically opposite changes to cardiac collagen content occurring in HF in the young and aged animals. Although in the present study collagen content was determined histologically, we and others have verified this technique against biochemical quantification of collagen in a previous publications and have shown a strong correlation between the two methodologies [3,36,37]. Changes to myocardial collagen content in HF have been reported previously in many studies of experimental HF with some showing an increase in myocardial collagen content [4,38] and others a decrease at the point of symptomatic HF [3,13,39]. Importantly however, none of these studies investigated

the importance of aging in the response of the ECM to HF. Considering the potential mechanisms underlying the age-dependent changes in cardiac ECM collagen content in HF, the increase of MMP-2 activity occurring in both aging and HF does not, by itself, provide sufficient explanation. However, the reduction of TIMP-3 and 4 that occur preferentially in the aged HF samples, and explicitly the correlation between MMP-2 activity and TIMP-4 protein, provide a possible mechanism for the specific loss of myocardial collagen in the aged HF cohort. However, as TIMP expression was not increased in either the young failing or aged control groups, this mechanism cannot account for the collagen accumulation which was measured in these experimental groups (Fig. 2). We used three experimental approaches to investigate whether altered collagen processing and/or synthesis could explain this discrepancy. An increase in SPARC in aging suggests that the facilitation of mature collagen fibril formation from procollagen is enhanced in the aged myocardium, a finding which is supported by others [31]. Even though a significant increase in collagen type I mRNA was not established in the present model of HF, serum levels of PICP suggest collagen synthesis is increased in both young failing and aged failing hearts. Although this is an indirect technique for quantifying myocardial collagen deposition, serum PICP levels have been demonstrated to correlate with coronary sinus PICP levels and also myocardial collagen deposition [40,41]. Importantly, the increase in collagen synthesis in aged failing animals occurred to a similar extent to that in young failing animals. Furthermore, as TIMP expression is only reduced in the aged failing hearts, taken together this data suggests a mechanism for the divergent age-dependent collagen remodeling which occurs in this model of pacing-induced HF.

However, the observation that increased myocardial collagen in young failing animals could lead to similar (albeit less pronounced) symptoms of cardiac decompensation as that seen in aged failing animals which displayed diminished collagen content, was surprising. Several lines of experimental evidence give indications as to why this might be the case. Altered collagen cross-linking has been demonstrated to change systolic performance independent of total collagen content [42,43], as well as changes to collagen type I:III ratio [44]. Furthermore, modifications to the sarcomeric protein titin such as isoform switches and/or phosphorylation status would also influence passive stiffness and thus contractile function [45]. Further studies would be required to establish whether age-dependent changes in these factors are influencing functional and morphological changes demonstrated in this ovine model of HF.

4.3. Aging as a pathological mechanism for divergent ECM remodeling in heart failure

A key question regarding the divergent remodeling of the cardiac ECM that occurs in aging in response to tachypacing-induced HF relates to whether or not pre-existent alterations to the biochemical fingerprint of the aged myocardium facilitate these differential effects. Studies using transgenic and knockout mouse models suggest this is likely. For example, ablation of cardiac MMP-2 or MMP-9 attenuates cardiac remodeling post myocardial ischemia [21,46]. Conversely, knockout of each of the cardiac TIMPs (1–4) accelerates adverse cardiac remodeling after injury [18–20,47] – a phenotype which, in the case of TIMP-4, was rescued with a double knockout involving MMP-2 deletion [19]. Additionally, TIMP-4 knockout mice displayed reduced cardiac function at 20 months of age whereas young TIMP-4 knockouts had comparable echocardiographic parameters to age-matched wild-type littermates [19]. These data, together with the fact that TIMP-4 is the most prevalent TIMP in the myocardium, and serves to regulate MMP-2 activity with high affinity [48,49], provide additional evidence that superimposition of diminished TIMP-4 expression in the aged, failing myocardium could lead to enhanced ECM remodeling through loss of MMP-2 inhibition leading to cardiac dysfunction. Furthermore, as SPARC has been demonstrated to enhance MMP-2 activity [50,51], and SPARC expression was increased

in the aged sheep LV, this could lead to further collagen degradation in the aged failing myocardium.

4.4. Study limitations

While the data in the present manuscript clearly demonstrates the influence of aging on cardiac remodeling and collagen content in HF, we are unable to provide certain mechanical and functional information *e.g.* compliance changes, cardiac output and E/A ratios. This is due to the anatomical arrangement of the cardiac apex over the sternum in the sheep preventing attainment of trans-thoracic four-chamber apical views. We cannot discount the role of other determinants of ventricular mechanics *e.g.* collagen cross-linking, collagen type I:III ratio and titin isoform switches as playing a role in the divergent age-dependent response to the induction of tachypacing-induced HF. Furthermore, as the study has been carried out using only female sheep, we cannot discount a possible role for estrogen in the results reported, and thus differences which may be present in males.

4.5. Future directions

Further studies investigating the differences in myocardial mechanics in young and aged failing animals would build on the current hypothesis. For example, performing conductance catheterization post-pacing in both young and aged animals, would indicate whether age-dependent changes to myocardial collagen content manifests as divergent changes of myocardial stiffness/compliance and thus deterioration of diastolic function. Additional techniques, such as MRI, would be useful for calculating ejection fraction and myocardial stress–strain relationships but are beyond the scope of the present study.

4.6. Conclusions

The main conclusion from the present study is that age has a critically important impact on the response of the myocardium to a disease-causing insult, in this case, tachypacing. As a consequence of these observations we suggest that age should be considered both in experimental cardiac research and in the development of therapeutic interventions aimed at correcting cardiac ECM remodeling in heart disease.

Conflict of interest

None declared.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at doi:10.1016/j.jmcc.2012.03.011.

References

- [1] Kannel WB. Risk stratification in hypertension: new insights from the Framingham study. *Am J Hypertens* 2000;13:3S–10S.
- [2] Caulfield JB, Borg TK. The collagen network of the heart. *Lab Invest* 1979;40:364–72.
- [3] Graham HK, Trafford AW. Spatial disruption and enhanced degradation of collagen with the transition from compensated ventricular hypertrophy to symptomatic congestive heart failure. *Am J Physiol* 2007;292:H1364–72.
- [4] Jalil JE, Doering CW, Janicki JS, Pick R, Shroff SG, Weber KT. Fibrillar collagen and myocardial stiffness in the intact hypertrophied rat left ventricle. *Circ Res* 1989;64:1041–50.
- [5] Robinson TF, Factor SM, Sonnenblick EH. The heart as a suction pump. *Sci Am* 1986;254:84–91.
- [6] Baicu CF, Stroud JD, Livesay VA, Hapke E, Holder J, Spinale FG, et al. Changes in extracellular collagen matrix alter myocardial systolic performance. *Am J Physiol* 2003;284:H122–32.
- [7] Burgess ML, Buggy J, Price RL, Abel FL, Terracio L, Samarel AM, et al. Exercise- and hypertension-induced collagen changes are related to left ventricular function in rat hearts. *Am J Physiol Heart Circ Physiol* 1996;270:H151–9.
- [8] Brower GL, Gardner JD, Forman MF, Murray DB, Voloshenyuk T, Levick SP, et al. The relationship between myocardial extracellular matrix remodeling and ventricular function. *Eur J Cardiothorac Surg* 2006;30:604–10.
- [9] Spinale FG, Coker ML, Krombach SR, Mukherjee R, Hallak H, Houck WV, et al. Matrix metalloproteinase inhibition during the development of congestive heart failure: effects on left ventricular dimensions and function. *Circ Res* 1999;85:364–76.
- [10] Conrad CH, Brooks WW, Hayes JA, Sen S, Robinson KG, Bing OHL. Myocardial fibrosis and stiffness with hypertrophy and heart failure in the spontaneously hypertensive rat. *Circulation* 1995;91:161–70.
- [11] Weber KT, Pick R, Jalil JE, Janicki JS, Carroll EP. Patterns of myocardial fibrosis. *J Mol Cell Cardiol* 1989;21(Suppl. 5):121–31.
- [12] Querejeta R, Lopez B, Gonzalez A, Sanchez E, Larman M, Martinez Ubago JL, et al. Increased collagen type I synthesis in patients with heart failure of hypertensive origin: relation to myocardial fibrosis. *Circulation* 2004;110:1263–8.
- [13] Spinale FG, Coker ML, Thomas CVT, Walker JD, Mukherjee R, Hebbar L. Time dependent changes in matrix metalloproteinase activity and expression during the progression of congestive heart failure: relation to ventricular and myocyte function. *Circ Res* 1998;82:482–95.
- [14] Spinale FG, Zellner JL, Johnson WS, Eble DM, Munyer PD. Cellular and extracellular remodelling with the development and recovery from tachycardia induced cardiomyopathy: changes in fibrillar collagen, myocyte adhesion capacity and proteoglycans. *J Mol Cell Cardiol* 1996;28:1591–608.
- [15] Dell'Italia LJ, Balcells E, Meng QC, Su X, Schultz D, Bishop SP, et al. Volume-overload cardiac hypertrophy is unaffected by ACE inhibitor treatment in dogs. *Am J Physiol Heart Circ Physiol* 1997;273:H961–70.
- [16] Cappelli V, Forni R, Poggese C, Reggiani C, Ricciardi L. Age-dependent variations of diastolic stiffness and collagen content in rat ventricular myocardium. *Arch Int Physiol Biochim* 1984;92:93–106.
- [17] Cielik KA, Taffet GE, Carlson S, Hermsillo J, Trial J, Entman ML. Immune-inflammatory dysregulation modulates the incidence of progressive fibrosis and diastolic stiffness in the aging heart. *J Mol Cell Cardiol* 2011;50:248–56.
- [18] Ikonomidis JS, Hendrick JW, Parkhurst AM, Herron AR, Escobar PG, Dowdy KB, et al. Accelerated LV remodeling after myocardial infarction in TIMP-1-deficient mice: effects of exogenous MMP inhibition. *Am J Physiol* 2005;288:H149–58.
- [19] Koskivirta I, Kassiri Z, Rahkonen O, Kiviranta R, Oudit GY, McKee TD, et al. Mice with tissue inhibitor of metalloproteinases 4 (Timp4) deletion succumb to induced myocardial infarction but not to cardiac pressure overload. *J Biol Chem* 2010;285:24487–93.
- [20] Kandam V, Basu R, Abraham T, Wang X, Awad A, Wang W, et al. Early activation of matrix metalloproteinases underlies the exacerbated systolic and diastolic dysfunction in mice lacking TIMP3 following myocardial infarction. *Am J Physiol Heart Circ Physiol* 2010;299:H1012–23.
- [21] Hayashidani S, Tsutsui H, Ikeuchi M, Shiomi T, Matsusaka H, Kubota T, et al. Targeted deletion of MMP-2 attenuates early LV rupture and late remodeling after experimental myocardial infarction. *Am J Physiol* 2003;285:H1229–35.
- [22] Lindsey ML, Goshorn DK, Squires CE, Escobar GP, Hendrick JW, Mingoa JT, et al. Age-dependent changes in myocardial matrix metalloproteinase/tissue inhibitor of metalloproteinase profiles and fibroblast function. *Cardiovasc Res* 2005;66:410–9.
- [23] Dibb KM, Rueckschloss U, Eisner DA, Isenberg G, Trafford AW. Mechanisms underlying enhanced cardiac excitation contraction coupling observed in the senescent sheep myocardium. *J Mol Cell Cardiol* 2004;37:1171–81.
- [24] Briston SJ, Caldwell JL, Horn MA, Clarke JD, Richards MA, Greensmith DJ, et al. Impaired β -adrenergic responsiveness accentuates dysfunctional excitation contraction coupling in an ovine model of tachypacing induced heart failure. *J Physiol* 2011;589:1367–82.
- [25] Dibb KM, Clarke JD, Horn MA, Richards MA, Graham HK, Eisner DA, et al. Characterization of an extensive transverse tubular network in sheep atrial myocytes and its depletion in heart failure. *Circ Heart Fail* 2009;2:482–9.
- [26] Cawston TE, Koshy P, Rowan AD. Assay of matrix metalloproteinases against matrix substrates. In: Clark IM, editor. *Matrix Metalloproteinase Protocols*. New Jersey: Humana Press Inc; 2001. p. 389–97.
- [27] Díaz ME, Graham HK, Trafford AW. Enhanced sarcolemmal Ca^{2+} efflux reduces sarcoplasmic reticulum Ca^{2+} content and systolic Ca^{2+} in cardiac hypertrophy. *Cardiovasc Res* 2004;62:538–47.

- [28] Walden AP, Dibb KM, Trafford AW. Differences in intracellular calcium homeostasis between atrial and ventricular myocytes. *J Mol Cell Cardiol* 2009;46:463–73.
- [29] Jarvis MD, Rademaker MT, Ellmers LJ, Currie MJ, McKenzie JL, Palmer BR, et al. Comparison of infarct-derived and control ovine cardiac myofibroblasts in culture: response to cytokines and natriuretic peptide receptor expression profiles. *Am J Physiol Heart Circ Physiol* 2006;291:H1952–8.
- [30] Rentz TJ, Poobalarahi F, Bornstein P, Sage EH, Bradshaw AD. SPARC regulates processing of procollagen I and collagen fibrillogenesis in dermal fibroblasts. *J Biol Chem* 2007;282:22062–71.
- [31] Bradshaw AD, Baicu CF, Rentz TJ, Van Laer AO, Bonnema DD, Zile MR. Age-dependent alterations in fibrillar collagen content and myocardial diastolic function: role of SPARC in post-synthetic procollagen processing. *Am J Physiol Heart Circ Physiol* 2010;298:H614–22.
- [32] Yarbrough WM, Spinale FG. Large animal models of congestive heart failure: a critical step in translating basic observations into clinical applications. *J Nucl Cardiol* 2003;10:77–86.
- [33] Sangaralingham SJ, Huntley BK, Martin FL, McKie PM, Bellavia D, Ichiki T, et al. The aging heart, myocardial fibrosis, and its relationship to circulating C-type natriuretic peptide. *Hypertension* 2011;57:201–7.
- [34] Jugdutt BI, Jelani A, Palaniyappan A, Idikio H, Uweira RE, Menon V, et al. Aging-related early changes in markers of ventricular and matrix remodeling after reperfused ST-segment elevation myocardial infarction in the canine model: effect of early therapy with an angiotensin II type 1 receptor blocker. *Circulation* 2010;122:341–51.
- [35] Raya TE, Gaballa M, Anderson P, Goldman S. Left ventricular function and remodeling after myocardial infarction in aging rats. *Am J Physiol Heart Circ Physiol* 1997;273:H2652–8.
- [36] James J, Bosch KS, Zuyderhoudt FMJ, Houtkooper JM, Gool J. Histophotometric estimation of volume density of collagen as an indication of fibrosis in rat liver. *Histochem Cell Biol* 1986;85:129–33.
- [37] van Westrhenen R, de Waart DR, Akman S, Krediet RT. Assessment of peritoneal fibrosis by conventional light microscopy and hydroxyproline measurements. *Perit Dial Int* 2004;24:290–2.
- [38] Fedak PW, Altamentova SM, Weisel RD, Nili N, Ohno N, Verma S, et al. Matrix remodeling in experimental and human heart failure: a possible regulatory role for TIMP-3. *Am J Physiol* 2003;284:H626–34.
- [39] King MK, Coker ML, Goldberg A, McElmurray III JH, Gunasinghe HR, Mukherjee R, et al. Selective matrix metalloproteinase inhibition with developing heart failure: effects on left ventricular function and structure. *Circ Res* 2003;92:177–85.
- [40] Martos R, Baugh J, Ledwidge M, O'Loughlin C, Conlon C, Patle A, et al. Diastolic heart failure: evidence of increased myocardial collagen turnover linked to diastolic dysfunction. *Circulation* 2007;115:888–95.
- [41] Gonzalez A, Lopez B, Ravassa S, Beaumont J, Arias T, Hermida N, et al. Biochemical markers of myocardial remodeling in hypertensive heart disease. *Cardiovasc Res* 2009;81:509–18.
- [42] Woodiwiss AJ, Tsotetsi OJ, Sprott S, Lancaster EJ, Mela T, Chung ES, et al. Reduction in myocardial collagen cross-linking parallels left ventricular dilatation in rat models of systolic chamber dysfunction. *Circulation* 2001;103:155–60.
- [43] Badenhorst D, Maseko M, Tsotetsi OJ, Naidoo A, Brooksbank R, Norton GR, et al. Cross-linking influences the impact of quantitative changes in myocardial collagen on cardiac stiffness and remodeling in hypertension in rats. *Cardiovasc Res* 2003;57:632–41.
- [44] Pauschinger M, Knopf D, Petschauer S, Doerner A, Poller W, Schwimmbeck PL, et al. Dilated cardiomyopathy is associated with significant changes in collagen type I/III ratio. *Circulation* 1999;99:2750–6.
- [45] LeWinter MM, Granzier H. Cardiac titin: a multifunctional giant. *Circulation* 2010;121:2137–45.
- [46] Heymans S, Lupu F, Terclavers S, Vanwetswinkel B, Herbert JM, Baker A, et al. Loss or inhibition of uPA or MMP-9 attenuates LV remodeling and dysfunction after acute pressure overload in mice. *Am J Pathol* 2005;166:15–25.
- [47] Kandalam V, Basu R, Abraham T, Wang X, Soloway PD, Jaworski DM, et al. TIMP2 deficiency accelerates adverse post-myocardial infarction remodeling because of enhanced MT1–MMP activity despite lack of MMP2 activation. *Circ Res* 2010;106:796–808.
- [48] Greene J, Wang M, Liu YE, Raymond LA, Rosen C, Shi YE. Molecular cloning and characterization of human tissue inhibitor of metalloproteinase 4. *J Biol Chem* 1996;271:30375–80.
- [49] Troeberg L, Tanaka M, Wait R, Shi YE, Brew K, Nagase H. E. coli expression of TIMP-4 and comparative kinetic studies with TIMP-1 and TIMP-2: insights into the interactions of TIMPs and matrix metalloproteinase 2 (gelatinase A). *Biochemistry* 2002;41:15025–35.
- [50] McClung HM, Thomas SL, Osenkowski P, Toth M, Menon P, Raz A, et al. SPARC upregulates MT1–MMP expression, MMP-2 activation, and the secretion and cleavage of galectin-3 in U87MG glioma cells. *Neurosci Lett* 2007;419:172–7.
- [51] Gilles C, Bassuk JA, Pulyaeva H, Sage EH, Foidart JM, Thompson EW. SPARC/osteonectin induces matrix metalloproteinase 2 activation in human breast cancer cell lines. *Cancer Res* 1998;58:5529–36.